

GPU Accelerated Real Time Polarimetric Image Processing through the use of CUDA

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Abstract— Recent advancements in semi-conductor fabrication has led to a dramatic increase in the size of data sets of advanced imaging sensors. While increased pixel counts leads to greater area coverage and higher resolution, it also results in higher image processing time. If real-time image processing is required, power and size requirements go up as large data processing computers are required to keep pace with the data. In this paper, we propose using desktop Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) to shrink the Size, Weight and Power (SWaP) pyramid. We have developed a novel approach to computing polarimetric data using GPUs. The GPU is inherently designed to perform parallel floating point operations quickly. Image processing is very well suited to the GPU architecture, where every pixel can be represented as a thread and all threads executed concurrently on the GPU. The processing of polarized imagery requires calculating the Stokes parameters and Degree of Linear Polarization (DoLP) of each pixel in the Focal Plane Array (FPA) of a sensor. In addition, dead pixel replacement is also desired in order to achieve better image contrast and create a higher quality image. Processing this data for large FPAs in Matlab takes as much as 30 seconds per frame, even after optimizing through vectorization. The Matlab code to process the polarized imagery was re-coded in NVidia's C API named CUDA and functions were run on an NVidia 9400 GS GPU with 64 cores. Massive speedup was attained, reducing the time to process a frame from 30 seconds in Matlab to 50 ms in CUDA, a speedup of 600x. In this paper we show that through use of the GPU we are able to accomplish real-time image processing using advanced algorithms, while at the same time reducing system SWaP requirements.

Keywords—*CUDA, GPU, polarimetry, micro-grid, image processing*

I. INTRODUCTION

Polarimetric imaging (PI) has great significance for defense related purposes. It can more easily detect targets in clutter that are at or near ambient temperature than standard IR imaging. However, PI has its drawbacks as well. PI is more sensitive to the non-uniformity of pixels and as a result, a good calibration is needed every time the camera is used for certain wavelengths. In addition, bad pixels can seriously deteriorate the quality of a DoLP image. These factors can and are corrected with advanced algorithms, but at the cost of high computational complexity. As a result, using standard Matlab procedures, approximately 30 seconds are required to process a

single frame. In order to create a real-time system that shows the DoLP image at 30 frames per second (fps), a radically new method was required. Parallel processing has been known to reduce computation time by splitting up a problem into pieces and solving the pieces concurrently. A modern GPU was used instead of the traditional Central Processing Unit (CPU) of the computer to run the PI algorithms. With 64 cores running concurrently, upto 29 fps was achieved.

II. BACKGROUND ON CUDA AND GPGPU

In the past few years, there has been an upsurge of development in multi-core computing. With clock speeds driving transistors to thermal limits, the multi-core approach was the obvious solution to extending Moore's Law [1]. GPU developers have taken that approach to extremes, with GPUs commercially available that consist of hundreds of cores. As the name implies, GPUs mostly deal with graphics and images. Usually, every pixel of an image is processed the same way with the same instruction. GPUs take advantage of this by parallelizing the processing. Each pixel is represented by a single thread and each thread of the image has the exact same instruction. These threads, often numbering in the millions, are then acted on by the dozens or hundreds of cores in the GPU concurrently. The results are then stitched back together to form the resulting image.

In 2007, the GPU developer NVidia launched a C API called the Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) to help developers with parallel programming. As it works in conjunction with the C and C++ languages that developers are already familiar with, CUDA has rapidly gained acceptance.

III. PI PARALLEL PROGRAMMING DEVELOPMENT

Our PI algorithm development is done on Matlab, which offers a host of impressive mathematical functions and debugging tools for image processing. In order to interface with the GPU, the Matlab code was first ported over to C. Initially, an NVidia GeForce 9400 GS with 64 cores was used. However, when integrating the Pleora Technologies framegrabber, a multi-core computer was needed. This computer came with an NVidia Quadro FX3800M with 128 cores. All timing results in this paper will be from the latter

GPU. Also, from here on, the CPU will be referred to as the host.

Initially, a frame was read on the host side and was transferred to the GPU for processing. Memory transfer was one of the largest bottlenecks for our programming. The impact of memory transfers was reduced by only transferring the memory from host to GPU once per frame and performing all of the computation on the GPU side to include display of results to the monitor. Results were transferred back to the host only when the user wanted to record data.

In Matlab, processing a 2D image without vectorization can be done by using a double for loop as shown in Algorithm 1. Parallel processing functions in CUDA only have the instruction for a single thread. This is then copied and executed by every thread, on different pieces of information, in this case: pixels. The user first defines the number of threads and how these threads are allocated amongst multiprocessors. Each multiprocessor is a group of 8 cores on the NVidia architecture. Then the program calls a CUDA function, which typically contains only the instructions within the double for loop in Algorithm 1, omitting the for loops.

Algorithm 1 Typical image processing algorithm structure in Matlab without vectorization

```

for row = 1 to m do
    for col = 1 to m do
        Process a pixel
    end for
end for

```

Most functions were converted to this format. The GPU has two types of memory: global that is accessed by any multiprocessor, and shared that is accessed only by the threads of the multiprocessor. While shared memory is more restrictive, it is also 100x faster than global memory. Wherever possible, global memory was moved to shared, actions were performed on the shared memory and finally, shared was copied back to global.

Single precision functions are upto 10x faster than double precision on the GPU. As a result, single precision was used for PI processing on the GPU. As shown in Figure , results between a non-uniformity corrected image in single and double precision had negligible difference. This picture displays a building with various targets layed out before it.

One problem with using CUDA and C instead of Matlab was the lack of built in linear algebra tools. For example, when calibrating the sensor for non-uniformity correction, a second order polynomial line fit is required for every pixel. This line fit requires a matrix inverse calculation. No C function for inverse matrix was available, so the Lagrange polynomial fit was used, which does not require a matrix inverse. Results are shown in Figure . Figure 1(a) shows the

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Comparison of NUC corrected imagery from the GPU with single precision (a) and Matlab with double precision (b)

IR image after Lagrange polynomial fit, and figure 1(b) shows the IR image with Matlab's polyfit function. There is almost no visible difference and the Lagrange polynomial fit does not degrade the quality of the DoLP image.

Afterward, in order to reduce Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) error, we used method four from [2]. This algorithm in Matlab uses the conv2 convolution function once for each wire-grid orientation as well as a deconvolution step.

It was found that convolution on the GPU took over 100 ms for each function call. To overcome this, for each pixel, an interpolation mask described in [2] was used to create 4 interpolated values, one for each orientation. This was then used to calculate the Stokes vectors and DoLP image. The DoLP image is shown in Figure .

Figure 2: DoLP image produced by the GPU

The GPU executes instructions in sets of 32 threads, which is called a warp. As a result, memory reads where all 32 threads read global memory that is sequentially spaced is faster as it is *coalesced memory* [3]. This is usually 8-10x faster than non-coalesced memory, based on timing tests. This was experienced first-hand when doing dead pixel correction. Initially, the function would only read memory for dead pixels in order to correct them. With only 3.5% dead pixels on the FPA, we thought that this would greatly reduce global memory accesses. However, during execution, it was revealed that this function was taking as much as 30 ms to complete. The function was re-written so that all threads would read global memory, regardless of whether they were dead pixels. In this case, as the FPA dimensions were multiples of 32, function execution time was reduced to 12-14 ms. This can be explained by the way that memory is read in the GPU. Our GPU has 512 bit global memory bus. A half warp or 16 32 bit floating point digits can be read through this bus with a single memory access, all at once as opposed to individually through the former method. According to the [4], memory reads of thread blocks in sizes that are multiples of 16 can take advantage of coalesced memory.

One of the difficulties we had to overcome when porting Matlab functions to C is the lack of certain native commands.

Figure 1: Parallel Reduction algorithm on the GPU

Table 1: Speed comparison of Matlab vs CUDA

Function Name	Matlab (s)	CUDA (ms)
Process 1 frame	43.216	49.029
Read in 10 frames	8.075	18.427
Get std dev of pixels across 10 frames and find dead pixels	2.953	15.685
Lagrange polynomial fit and find dead pixels	2.631	7.698
Fix Dead Pixels	4.56	0.313
Split Intensity orientations and calculate Stokes Vectors	4.38	6.819
Standard Deviation of a frame	0.463	6.849

Matlab provides very powerful and useful functions for averaging an array, finding standard deviation and others. In order to do bad pixel correction, the frame average was required. Adding all the pixels of an array is an inherently serial problem, where each value is sequentially added to a running total. However, this serial method would be too expensive on a GPU. The CUDA Software Development Kit (SDK) provides a function for parallel reduction where reduction is accomplished in stages. In the first stage, every other thread adds the pixel value next to it, lead to $N/2$ total partial sums, if N is the total number of pixels. Subsequent identical stages are employed on ever increasingly smaller numbers of partial sums until a single value is reached. An example of this method is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Thus in $O(\log(n))$ step, the total is calculated. This method was adopted for use with our program and functions were created for frame average and frame standard deviation that allowed us to identify bad pixels in the FPA.

IV. RESULTS

Matlab and CUDA profiler functions allow the user to run his code and gather the execution time for the various functions that are part of the program. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a speed comparison of CUDA vs Matlab. It is important to note that the CUDA results are in milliseconds and the Matlab results are in seconds. On average most functions were over 500x faster when processed on the GPU. Overall, processing took 33.63 ms on CUDA, which translates to 29.72 fps.

All raw data in both Matlab and CUDA were stored on the hard drive and *post-processed* meaning that they were not

processed in real-time straight from the camera. As a result, hard drive latency was the same for both Matlab and CUDA. Even so, simply reading a 1mega-pixel frame without any processing was faster with CUDA than Matlab. This is due to CUDA using C which is closer to the hardware than Matlab, which uses Java.

In order to find dead pixels, we needed the standard deviation of each pixel across 10 frames to find outliers. We must remember that this calculation involves calculations over 10 1kx1k frames or 10 mega-pixels, a considerable amount of data. Matlab's built in function performed reasonably fast at nearly 3s. However, CUDA performed the same function in 15.685 ms.

Finding the polynomial fit for the pixels and dead pixels were combined in one function. Here the values were converted from digital counts to radiance using Non-Uniformity Correction (NUC) data. CUDA performed 341x faster here as well.

After the dead pixels are found, three iterations of pixel fixing function were run. After the optimization described in section III, this was massively reduced to only .313 ms. Matlab took considerably longer, in part due to the fact that we were not able to vectorize the function. As a result, in Matlab this function was run with a double for loop, resulting in a longer execution time.

After the polynomial fit, the different intensity values needed to be split up. This would create 4 frames from the original one, one for each of the following orientations: 0°, 45°, 90° and 135°. Then the interpolation technique described in [1] was used to return each sub-frame to the original resolution. Splitting the orientations into 4 frames allows for simple calculation of the Stokes vectors in the GPU. Typically for FPGA implementations of PI processing, a major concern is the time required for the square-root and division operations required to calculate the DoLP. Some implementations of the hardware units for these can take thousands of clock cycles. However, the GPU required only 6.819 ms per frame to split the orientations and calculate the Stokes values. This is partially due to the extremely fast floating point units (FPU) that GPUs have in each of their cores relative to the FPUs in CPUs.

Finally, calculating the standard deviation of a frame is timed. The code called for 4 different places where the frame needed to be summed, including for standard deviation. It was noted that the first time the parallel summation function was called for a frame, it took almost 10 ms, however every other call took about 1ms. This *warm-up* time for the summation process could not be explained.

V. RENDERING WITH OPENGL

After processing, we wanted to display the results for the user to see the results as they were being calculated. For this, we chose to use the OpenGL standard for computer graphics and rendering. OpenGL provides some useful tools such as shading, and split window display. However, most importantly, all OpenGL functions run directly on the GPU and do not need much help from the host. The rendering from

OpenGL is then displayed directly on the monitor from the GPU without having to transfer any memory back to the host.

In order to display the product to the screen, the floating point DoLP and IR images needed to be normalized to an 8-bit gray-scale image. After that, the images were displayed to the user in a window consisting of 3 sub images. The first was the DoLP image, the second is the IR image. The third used an OpenGL transparency function that allowed us to superimpose the DoLP image over the IR image. This was done by first drawing the IR image in grayscale. Then the DoLP image was drawn in green color over it. The amount of transparency of the green color was determined by the magnitude of DoLP. So a highly polarized target would show up more green and less polarized targets would be more grayscale. This was done in real time and took an extra 7ms if memory transfer time is included.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we showed that it is possible to drastically reduce computation time for complex PI algorithms using the parallel processing power of COTS GPUs. Many algorithms were easily ported from Matlab to C. However, there were several cases where built-in Matlab functions were sorely missed and alternatives had to be created from scratch. In particular are simple functions such as array sum, standard deviation and convolution.

Now that we have a library of basic array functionality, we should be able to more rapidly develop CUDA GPU code. The CUDA code has been written for integration with a frame-grabber to allow for real-time image display. This will soon be tested when integrated with the polarimetric camera. When switching between the low-end GeForce 9400 GS GPU to the high-end Quadro FX3800M GPU, we doubled the number of cores, but did not double the frame rate. We only got a 34% speedup. This could be due to near constant memory latency which cannot be easily reduced. A trade study needs to be conducted to see where increasing cores can help, and where a cheaper alternative will yield the same results in our image processing.

VII. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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